

Report on Repository Support for Data-Level Interoperability / Reusability

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Executive summary

The [EOSC Association FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force](#) surveyed **39 research data repositories** between April and September 2025 to assess FAIR data management practices and readiness for integration with the EOSC Federation. This study provides the first indicative empirical baseline of FAIR data management practices in European research data repositories. It informs the Task Force's ongoing work on data-level reusability metrics and the [EOSC Federation Handbook](#), as well as the technical specifications for interoperability co-developed with the [OSTrails project](#).

The analysis covers **seven analytical domains**: metadata practices, licensing, persistent identifiers, provenance tracking, FAIR assessment, policy governance and sustainability, and EOSC Federation alignment – derived from six thematic survey sections (Sections 2–6). Section 1 (Demographics) provides repository profiling context used throughout for cross-tabulation. Respondents represented a broad cross-section of repository types (generalist, disciplinary – covering a scientific domain, thematic – covering certain data categories like imaging, institutional – covering datasets from an organisational unit, Digital Object-specific – covering certain kinds of digital objects like workflows and mixed-type), geographic regions, and organisational models, including both EOSC-affiliated and independent repositories.

This survey is based on self-reported data from repository managers. Due to resource limitations, it was not possible to systematically validate those reports, though TF members did note what they believed were discrepancies between some of the answers provided and the implemented capabilities of the repository when they examined it themselves. These included examples where terminology was not being consistently interpreted between respondents, or when the meaning of the term when used by TF members differed from the interpretation of that term by the respondent (e.g. the definitions of machine-actionable versus machine-readable). There were also cases where positive responses to certain questions (for example, about data-file-level metadata) were found to be only minimally accurate when manually validated by TF members, but not consistent with the *intent* of the question to measure readiness for data-level reuse.

The sample represents repositories actively engaged with FAIR principles and EOSC initiatives. As such, there will be some bias in this sample and these findings may not generalise to all European repositories. Response rates varied by question, with some technical questions receiving substantially fewer responses compared to demographic aspects.

Taken together, these caveats revealed that interpreting FAIR maturity requires careful consideration of possible validation mechanisms, particularly if self-reported capabilities are used to assess federation readiness. Indeed, this is being addressed by the OSTrails project, where automated FAIR assessment infrastructure is being designed that can not only do assessments at-scale, but is also significantly more community-aware and DO-specific than the offerings of most current mechanized FAIR assessment tools.

Across the six analytical domains, findings were assessed against three levels of capability maturity: **human-readable provision** (information available to users but requiring manual interpretation), **machine-readable formats** (structured data that can be parsed computationally), and **machine-actionable specifications** (semantic standards enabling automated reasoning, rights

verification, and provenance inference). This three-level distinction underpins the identification of capability gaps throughout the report.

The survey findings suggested **widespread maturity in basic FAIR infrastructure**:

- **100%** of repositories assign persistent identifiers at the dataset level (97% using DOIs).
- **92%** provide licenses at the record level.
- **90%** validate metadata and **74%** share it with aggregators such as OpenAIRE and DataCite.
- **78%** align with EOSC Federation principles (e.g., distributed governance, federation of services, shared policies) and report willingness to participate.

However, the results also revealed **persistent and systemic gaps that may limit automated data-level reusability and computational federation integration**. Specifically, the results indicate that:

- **64%** of repositories reported using machine-readable or machine-processable license formats, although more advanced semantic approaches remained rare.
- Only **18%** reported applying standard vocabularies and methods (e.g., PROV-O, RO-Crate) for provenance, despite **72%** internally tracking information such as data creation, generation processes, and version history.
- **51%** reported supporting file-level persistent identifiers (PIDs), leaving a substantial gap compared with dataset-level coverage.
- **11%** reported making policies available in machine-readable formats, despite **95%** maintaining documented governance frameworks, suggesting that policy visibility and structured exposure remain limited.

The findings suggest a clear gap between **FAIR readiness for discovery at the deposit level** and **FAIR readiness for reuse at the file or object level**, the latter being the more operationally relevant dimension for EOSC Federation services, whose organisational, operational, and technical requirements demand a depth of FAIR implementation that metadata-level discoverability alone cannot satisfy. Repositories are generally stronger in exposing deposit-level metadata, identifiers, and basic licensing information that support discovery and access. By contrast, the more granular and structured information needed to support reuse across systems—such as file-level identifiers, file-level metadata, provenance, and explicit rights conditions—remains uneven. The central issue is therefore not only whether FAIR information is machine-readable or machine-actionable, but whether FAIR implementation extends from **deposit-level discovery** to **file-level reusability**.

The survey indicates that most repositories endorse the principles of the EOSC Federation model but require targeted support such as technical guidance, capacity building, and sustained funding to extend FAIR implementation from discovery-oriented deposit-level practices toward more reuse-oriented, interoperable support at the file or object level.

This study thus provides a first attempt at building empirical foundations for **transitioning from repository-level FAIR assessment to data-level reusability evaluation**, aligning directly with the [Task Force's Key Focus Areas](#) and the [OSTrails FAIR Interoperability Framework \(FAIR-IF\)](#). The evidence supports prioritising five priority interventions:

1. **Object-Level Granularity for PIDs and Rights Expression**
2. **Provenance Interoperability through Standard Vocabularies and Methods**
3. **Policy Availability and Clarity in Metadata**
4. **Shared EOSC Glossary for Operational Terminology and Use Cases**
5. **Capacity Building and Sustained Support for FAIR Implementation**

Together, these priorities will enable repositories to evolve from **deposit-oriented, discovery-focused** platforms toward **DO-oriented, reuse-ready** participation in the EOSC Federation where data interoperability, automation, and reusability enhance scientific knowledge production.

Introduction

The FAIR principles (Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability) emerged in 2016 as foundational guidelines for managing research data in an increasingly digital and data-intensive scientific landscape (Wilkinson et al., 2016). Initially articulated to address challenges in data discovery and access, the principles rapidly gained traction across the global research community, becoming embedded in research funder mandates, institutional policies, and infrastructure development strategies. The European Commission's adoption of FAIR as a cornerstone of its Open Science policy, particularly through the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) initiative, positioned FAIR implementation as central to Europe's vision for a federated research data infrastructure enabling cross-border and cross-disciplinary scientific collaboration.

However, a decade of FAIR implementation efforts has revealed a fundamental limitation in how the principles have been operationalised in practice. According to [FAIRAssist](#), more than 30 Assessment frameworks have been developed to measure FAIR compliance but they are predominantly focused on repository-level infrastructure and metadata discoverability rather than on data-level reusability. Repositories achieving high FAIR scores via/using those assessment frameworks demonstrate strong capabilities for discovery: their datasets appear in search engines, possess persistent identifiers, provide descriptive metadata, and documented license terms. Yet these same repositories often lack the granular, structured, and interoperable information needed to support reuse beyond discovery, especially at the file or Digital Object (DO) level, where rights, provenance, content description, and object relationships become critical. This distinction – between **deposit-oriented** FAIR support focused on discovery and DO FAIR support focused on reuse – structures the analysis throughout this report.

This gap between discovery-oriented assessment and reusability-focused infrastructure is becoming increasingly apparent as the EOSC Federation develops. The [EOSC Association FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force](#)—established to develop assessment frameworks aligned with EOSC Federation requirements—explicitly identified in its Terms of Reference that *"current FAIR assessment is mainly focused on the FAIRness of the repository" and proves "insufficient for assessing the capability of data to be federated."* Furthermore, the Task Force argued for a strategic pivot toward metrics evaluating data-level reusability defined as *"the degree to which computational services can automatically determine whether specific datasets meet technical requirements for particular analytical workflows, comply with legal constraints, possess necessary quality attributes, and maintain traceable provenance"*.

This strategic shift to data-level reusability assessment requires empirical grounding by addressing some key questions, including: what capabilities do European repositories currently possess; where do implementation gaps exist between FAIR support for discovery at the deposit level and FAIR support for reuse at the file or object level; which technical dimensions show greatest deficits requiring prioritised intervention; and, how do repositories vary across organisational models, disciplinary contexts, and scales of operation? Without systematic baseline

measurements, it is difficult to specify what actions are required to advance FAIRness, rather than investing in domains where repositories already demonstrate strong capabilities, while neglecting areas with substantial gaps impeding federation integration.

This survey was designed to provide the empirical evidence base for the FAIR Metrics Task Force's strategic direction and to inform technical specifications under development by the [OSTrails project](#) (Open Science Plan-Track-Assess Pathways). The primary objective was determining the degree to which European research data repositories support—or are becoming ready to support—FAIR reusability of data deposits, with particular emphasis on the extent to which FAIR support extends from deposit-level discovery toward the more granular information and interoperability mechanisms needed to enable reuse across federated environments.

The survey instrument (See: [Appendix](#)), developed collaboratively by members of the FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force, addressed six survey sections following a logical progression from infrastructure description, through operational practices, to strategic alignment.

- **Demographics** questions (Survey Section 1) collected information necessary to profile repositories.
- **Technical Infrastructure** questions (Survey Section 2) examined metadata provision, license expression, and persistent identifier assignment—the foundational capabilities enabling automated discovery and rights assessment.
- **Operational Practices** questions (Survey Section 3) investigated day-to-day repository management, including metadata validation workflows, provenance tracking approaches, and FAIR assessment methodologies—distinguishing between stated policies and operational reality.
- **Policy and Governance** questions (Survey Section 4) evaluated institutional commitment through formal policy frameworks and strategic planning.
- **Sustainability** questions (Survey Section 5) assessed measures ensuring long-term viability beyond project funding cycles.
- **EOSC Federation** questions (Survey Section 6) explored philosophical alignment with federation principles, practical implementation barriers, and capacity requirements.

The survey also distinguished between three levels of capability maturity: (1) **human-readable provision**—information available to human users but requiring manual interpretation, (2) **machine-readable formats**—structured data that computational agents can parse but not necessarily reason about, and (3) **machine-actionable specifications**—semantic standards enabling automated reasoning, rights verification, and provenance inference. This three-level distinction proved essential for diagnosing precisely where implementation gaps occurred: repositories might provide license information (provision), express it in structured JSON (machine-readable), yet do not implement semantic vocabularies (machine actionable), such as [Open Digital Rights Language](#) (ODRL) enabling automated permissions reasoning. However, the notion of “machine-actionable” may be interpreted differently across repository contexts, and the

absence of a strictly operationalised definition may have contributed to heterogeneity in reported capabilities.

The survey was distributed to 39 European research data repositories identified through FAIR Metrics Task Force members' networks and representing diverse organisational models, disciplinary scopes, and scales of operation. The sample included repositories affiliated with [EOSC Federation selected Nodes](#) (Candidate Nodes designated for Build-Up Group demonstration), repositories managed by EOSC Association Members, repositories operated by national Mandated Organizations coordinating member state engagement, and independent repositories operating outside formal EOSC structures. This diversity enabled assessment of whether EOSC organisational affiliation correlated with advanced FAIR capabilities or whether machine-actionable infrastructure distributed broadly across the European repository landscape regardless of formal federation status.

Importantly, this survey represents a coordinated effort across multiple complementary EOSC initiatives addressing different facets of repository infrastructure and federation readiness. The FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force Co-Chairs and several Task Force members are OSTrails consortium members, ensuring alignment between policy frameworks (Task Force strategic direction and Key Focus Areas) and technical implementation (OSTrails Interoperability Frameworks and pilot demonstrations). This organisational overlap enables rapid translation of empirical survey findings into technical specifications, with results informing both Task Force assessment framework development and OSTrails Year 2 revisions of the [FAIR Interoperability Framework \(FAIR-IF\)](#), [Data Management Plan Interoperability Framework \(DMP-IF\)](#), and [Scientific Knowledge Graph Interoperability Framework \(SKG-IF\)](#).

To maximise research impact and avoid duplication of effort across the EOSC ecosystem, the survey questionnaire was shared with the [FIDELIS project](#) (Establishing a European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories) during their survey design phase. Where this survey focuses on FAIR technical capability assessment—measuring machine-actionable infrastructure for metadata, licenses, identifiers, and provenance—FIDELIS examines repository trustworthiness, legal frameworks, organisational sustainability, and network building. The two surveys were conducted independently, but their deliberately aligned scope means their findings are complementary: this survey's quantification of machine-actionable infrastructure gaps can be read alongside FIDELIS's assessment of organisational capacity for a more complete picture of European repository readiness.

This study presents findings in five sections. Following this Introduction, the [1. Data Management and Methods section](#) describes survey design, participant recruitment, and analytical approaches. The [2. Results section](#) presents findings organised by the six analytical domains, with cross-tabulations by repository type where significant differences emerged. The [3. Discussion section](#) interprets findings, identifies systematic patterns, and contextualises results within the

broader EOSC landscape. The report [4. concludes with strategic recommendations](#) for strengthening repository infrastructure and EOSC Federation development.

1. Data management and methods

This study employed a survey in the form of interviews designed to assess current practices in FAIR data management in relation but not limited to EOSC Federation readiness among European research data repositories. The survey comprised 70 questions organised across six survey sections covering seven analytical domains: metadata practices, licensing, persistent identifiers, provenance tracking, FAIR assessment, policy governance, and EOSC alignment. Questions employed multiple formats including multiple-choice selections, Likert-scale ratings, and open-ended responses to capture both quantitative patterns and qualitative context.

The target population comprised research data repositories operating in Europe that manage, store, and provide access to digital research outputs. Repositories were identified and recruited through two complementary approaches: targeted outreach by Task Force (TF) members to repositories with which they had established relationships, and open invitations distributed through EOSC Association networks and community channels. Survey participation was voluntary. The final sample consisted of 39 repositories: generalist repositories serving all research domains (26%, n=10), discipline-specific repositories focused on particular fields (41%, n=16), thematic repositories organized around research topics (13%, n=5), and mixed or other types (20%, n=8). Among respondents, 41% were affiliated with EOSC Federation structures (Selected Nodes, Member institutions, or Mandated Organisations) while 59% operated outside formal federation frameworks. Response rates were not systematically tracked because the survey did not use a probability-based sample drawn from a predefined and exhaustive sampling frame. Instead, it relied on a convenience sampling approach, with participation solicited through EOSC-related networks, professional contacts, mailing lists, and stakeholder communities relevant to FAIR assessment tools and practices. In practical terms, this means that the survey was made available to potentially relevant participants through existing dissemination channels, rather than being sent to a closed and fully enumerated list of eligible respondents.

Data was collected using the [EU survey tool](#) from 15.04.2025 to 30.09.2025, when the recipients' data was downloaded for analysis. We followed two complementary methods to collect data: 1. individual interviews with repository managers who our TF members have outreach to, and 2. two focus group meetings inviting more repository managers for a guided writing and clarification session. In both formats, survey questions guided the conversation while allowing flexibility for participants to elaborate on practices and challenges. In total, there were 39 responses. In a small number of cases, responses were submitted at the organisational level rather than per repository. Two distinct situations arose. First, organisations managing multiple repositories submitted one response per repository, each treated as an independent observational unit given that repositories

within the same organisation may differ in their technical infrastructure, policies, and standards. Second, large distributed research infrastructures – such as CESSDA and CLARIN – submitted a single collective response representing all nodes in their network, on the basis that those nodes share common technical capabilities. In these cases, the collective response was counted as a single unit ($n=1$) in the analysis.

Upon collection, survey data were systematically pre-processed and analysed using [reproducible workflows](#) implemented in the R statistical environment. The EUSurvey tool provided basic results (frequencies, charts), but further data manipulation was needed, e.g., for cross tabulations. Data cleaning included harmonisation of acronyms and spellings, correction of typographical inconsistencies, removal of duplicates, and normalisation of categorical labels. Open-ended responses were reviewed and processed according to two complementary strategies: for selected questions, free-text inputs were categorised and recoded into structured variables suitable for tabular analysis; while in other cases the original textual responses were preserved and thematically organised to support a qualitative narrative synthesis alongside quantitative results. All data collection, interview facilitation, response categorisation, and analytical decisions described in this section were carried out by Task Force members, whose expertise spans repository management, research infrastructure architecture, FAIR assessment, data stewardship, and domain science.

All subsequent analytical steps were executed via scripted procedures written in R, enabling automated generation of descriptive statistics, proportional frequency tables, visualisations, and cross-tabulations. Multi-select questions were processed through algorithmic reconstruction of answer blocks, and cross-tab analyses were computed across combinations of single-choice and multi-selection variables using exclusively descriptive methods (counts and percentages) without inferential testing. Output tables and figures were produced programmatically in standard formats (CSV and PNG) to facilitate validation, reuse, and dissemination.

Variable metadata (question identifiers, labels, and recoding schemes) were integrated through dedicated mapping files, ensuring consistency between survey content and analytical representations while further supporting data anonymisation practices. By employing a fully script-based analytical pipeline, the entire workflow, from data cleaning to figure generation, remains reproducible and inspectable.

The figures present descriptive summaries of the survey responses and should be interpreted as frequency-based visualisations of how respondents answered each question. For single-answer questions, horizontal bar charts show the number of respondents selecting each response option. For multiple-selection questions, the charts display the number of respondents selecting each available option, noting that respondents may choose more than one option; therefore, the counts shown across options may sum to more than the number of respondents. Cross-tabulation figures explore the relationship between two questions. When both variables are single-answer questions, stacked bar charts show how responses to one question are distributed across the categories of

the other. When one or both questions allow multiple selections, heatmaps are used to represent the proportion of respondents selecting a given option within each category. In these cases, colour intensity reflects the percentage of respondents selecting the option among those considered for the cross-tabulation. In all figures, axis titles are omitted for visual clarity and are explained in the accompanying captions.

Figures and visualisations of the processed data were made available in the same TF folder. Re-identification possibilities and risks associated with data were considered and minimised through the anonymisation process. The anonymised dataset along with its supplementary material are available on [Zenodo](#).

2. Results

The primary objective of this survey was to determine the degree to which repositories supported (or were becoming ready to support) FAIR reusability of data deposits. This required investigating capabilities across seven analytical domains, organised across six survey sections (see: Annex).

1. **Respondents Profile:** The survey first established baseline characteristics of participating repositories to enable meaningful interpretation of technical and operational findings. Questions addressed repository type (generalist, discipline-specific, thematic, mixed, other), organizational governance (university, government, private, non-profit, international), geographic location, scale (dataset holdings), and EOSC affiliation status. These profiling dimensions provided essential context for understanding the heterogeneous European research data repository landscape and interpreting variation in FAIR implementation patterns across different repository profiling dimensions.
2. **Technical Infrastructure:** The technical section examined infrastructure enabling automated discovery, processing, and interoperability, which are essential capabilities for EOSC Federation services and computational agents to evaluate data utility without human intervention.
 - **Metadata Standards and Practices:** Machine-discoverable and interpretable metadata about both deposits (identifiers, authorship) and deposit content (quality, experimental conditions, variables measured) form the foundation for automated data discovery and utility assessment. Historically, content-level metadata has been lacking, with only rare examples such as the [ELIXIR Investigation-Study-Assay \(ISA\) framework](#), launched in 2012 and matured into the [ISA-based MARS](#) providing predictable structures for data-level metadata advertisement. Presently, there are almost [2,000 \(meta\)data standards](#) across all disciplines. The questions measured the degree to which repositories provided access to these metadata types through predictable, machine-actionable discovery pathways, including metadata sources beyond DataCite minimum requirements, domain and community-specific metadata provision, standardized metadata formats (generic and community-specific), metadata discoverability from landing pages, file-level metadata assignment, metadata sharing with aggregators, harvesting protocols (OAI-PMH, REST API, SPARQL, OGC-CSW), and ontology/controlled vocabulary mapping.
 - **Licensing:** Transparency through machine-actionable license expression enables automated rights assessment and informed reuse decisions. Questions examined whether repositories made license information not only human-readable but also computationally interpretable through standards like SPDX and ODRL. Machine-actionability in licensing goes beyond mere discoverability: it requires licenses expressed in formats that software can interpret programmatically to determine permissions and restrictions automatically. The section addressed both data licenses and metadata licenses separately, recognizing their distinct legal implications, and evaluated license requirement policies, machine-discoverability, standardization ([SPDX License List](#) compliance), use of universally accepted GUIDs, machine-actionability standards (SPDX, ODRL, ccREL), and differentiation across metadata types (curated versus deposited, open versus authenticated access).
 - **Persistent Identifiers:** Identifier infrastructure at dataset and file levels support findability, citability, and persistent linking across research outputs. Questions

evaluated PID implementation granularity (dataset-level versus file-level assignment), PID types supported (DOI, Handle, ARK, OID, URN, PURL, other), resolver infrastructure used (handle.net, DataCite, local resolvers, other), and cross-referencing capabilities to related outputs (publications, software, data management plans, workflows). The survey recognised alternative approaches such as Signposting which is a web-linking approach that supports machine navigation across landing pages, metadata, and content resources.

3. Operational Practices: The operational section assessed how repositories actually operated day-to-day, their curation workflows, and systematic quality assurance processes, distinguishing between stated policies and operational reality.

- **Provenance:** Provenance tracking captures data lineage, creation processes, and version history essential for reproducibility assessment and informed reuse. Questions distinguished between repositories using standard vocabularies (W3C [PROV-O](#), [RO-Crate](#)) enabling automated provenance reasoning and those relying on internal non-standard approaches limiting cross-repository interoperability. Beyond technical standards, the section examined how provenance information was made available to users (metadata fields, landing pages, downloadable files, APIs), what contextual information repositories provided to support reusability (data dictionaries/codebooks, software/tools used, experimental methods, quality assurance procedures, version history/audit trails, licensing information), whether this information was captured in machine-readable formats (RO-Crate, JSON, ISA-JSON, RDF, other), and whether repositories linked datasets to related research outputs (publications, software, workflows). Questions also explored whether users could contribute enriched dataset versions back to repositories, reflecting collaborative curation models.
- **FAIR Metrics:** Systematic measurement of FAIR principle adherence reveals the gap between conceptual endorsement and operational implementation. Questions investigated whether repositories assessed FAIRness systematically (yes, no, partially); which specific FAIR dimensions they evaluated (licensing clarity, metadata richness, provenance, interoperability); which tools and methodologies they employed in practice; what aspects related to reusability they monitored (dataset citations, downloads/views, provenance completeness, metadata completeness/accuracy, license clarity, standard format usage, interlinking with related outputs); what types of metrics would be useful but were currently unsupported; and what barriers prevented more rigorous assessment (lack of technical infrastructure, human resources/expertise, clear community standards, user demand, funding/support, difficulty integrating external tools). This distinguished between *ad hoc* informal assessments and methodologically rigorous systematic measurement integrated into repository workflows.

4. Policy and Governance: The policy section evaluated institutional commitment through formal policy frameworks, strategic planning, and alignment with broader research infrastructure initiatives.

- **General Policies:** Questions examined whether repositories followed community guidelines for interoperability (e.g., [OpenAIRE Guidelines](#)); which specific policy types they maintained (collection policy, preservation/data retention policy, open access file format policy, privacy policy, terms of use/deposit, ethical use policy, FAIR data policy, user registration/authentication policy, data curation policy,

security breach/incident response policy, data quality assessment procedure); and whether policies were machine-readable or exposed in metadata (e.g., schema.org, [FAIRsharing registration](#)). When implemented, policy machine-readability would enable automated compliance checking and policy discovery by federation services which remains an aspirational capability for most repositories in the current landscape.

- **Rules and Regulations:** Questions addressed legal regulations affecting user access to repository data ([GDPR](#), Cloud Act, [CIR High Value Datasets](#), [Data Governance Act](#), [EHDS](#), other), and whether repositories implemented regular review cycles for data records (yearly, other intervals, none). This revealed how external regulatory frameworks shape repository operations and whether systematic curation occurs on defined schedules versus ad-hoc approaches.
5. **Sustainability:** The sustainability section examined measures ensuring repositories' long-term viability beyond project funding cycles. Questions addressed whether external organizations/entities operated the repository and their organizational type (private company, university/research organization, government body, international body, other), and which sustainability measures repositories employed (long-term funding, community involvement, collaborations, data preservation strategies, open access initiatives, regular audits/evaluations, user training/support, other). These indicators reveal institutional embedment and resource security essential for sustained FAIR infrastructure operation.
 6. **EOSC Federation:** The EOSC Federation section explored alignment with federation principles, practical implementation challenges, and capacity requirements, revealing readiness for European research infrastructure integration. Questions examined whether repositories agreed with EOSC Federation model principles (distributed governance, federation of services, shared policies); solicited open-ended perspectives on the federation approach and whether it could work for their repository and community (including technical, policy-related, human resource, or other challenges); and asked what support would help repositories better align with EOSC initiatives and policies (technical guidance, funding, community building, no support needed, cannot accept support, other).

Response rates varied systematically across the six survey sections described above. Questions covering well-established operational practices, such as metadata provision, persistent identifiers, and policy governance, received most responses by repository managers. By contrast, certain technically specific questions, particularly those requiring detailed knowledge of licensing standards, FAIR assessment tooling, or machine-actionable implementations, received lower response rates, reflecting the specialised nature of these topics across respondents.

Most question categories got high response (95-100%, n=37-39/39): Demographics, Technical Infrastructure—Metadata, Technical Infrastructure—PIDs, Operational Practices—Provenance, Operational Practices—FAIR Metrics, Policy and Governance, and EOSC Federation. Notably, Technical Infrastructure—Licenses showed variable response patterns, with most questions achieving high response but license modification rights receiving only 3 responses (8% response rate), likely reflecting the question's narrow applicability to repositories with specific modification workflows rather than universal relevance. Similarly, Operational Practices—General Metadata achieved near-universal response, but FAIR Metrics Q54 (specific FAIR assessment approaches and tools) received 21 responses (54% response rate); while 51% of repositories reported assessing FAIR metrics, only approximately half of those assessors provided methodological

details.

These variable response patterns are explicitly noted in relevant sections below, with findings from limited-response questions interpreted with appropriate caution, explicit sample size reporting, and acknowledgment that generalisability is constrained by response rates. Where open-ended questions yielded diverse responses requiring manual categorisation (e.g., Q11 metadata standards, Q45 provenance availability methods, Q69 EOSC barriers), the analytical approach is documented to enable reproducibility assessment.

2.1 Respondents Profile

The interviews reached **39 repository managers**. A small number of these repositories were managed by the same parent organisation, though each operated as a distinct service with separate policies and technical infrastructure.

Figure 1: Characteristics of respondents

Repository types comprised 16 discipline-specific repositories (41%), 8 institutional repositories (21%), 7 generalist repositories (18%), 4 project-based repositories (10%), and 3 repositories of other types (8%, including national and thematic services).

Geographic coverage was concentrated in Central and Northern Europe. Repositories operated from Germany (n=10, 26%), Switzerland (n=6, 15%), the Netherlands (n=4, 10%), and Nordic countries (n=7, 18% combined across Sweden, Norway, Finland, Denmark). Additional representation came from France (n=3), Austria (n=2), Belgium (n=2), Greece (n=2), and single repositories from Ireland, Poland, and the United Kingdom. The geographic distribution complemented representation from intergovernmental or pan-European infrastructures, reflecting the survey's reach across both national and transnational repository services.

Repository scale varied substantially. Dataset holdings ranged from under 100 datasets (n=8 repositories, 21%) to over 10,000 datasets (n=11 repositories, 28%), with intermediate ranges of 100-1,000 datasets (n=9, 23%) and 1,000-10,000 datasets (n=11, 28%). This distribution captured both specialised collections and large-scale aggregation services operating at European scale, enabling analysis of whether FAIR implementation patterns varied with repository size.

Organisational affiliation showed concentration in academic settings. The majority of repositories (n=25, 64%) operated under university governance, followed by research institutes (n=8, 21%), government agencies (n=3, 8%), and other organisational structures (n=3, 8%). This distribution reflected the academic-centered nature of European research data infrastructure, with complementary representation from non-profit organizations, international bodies, and private entities managing specialised research data services.

Importantly, nearly half of the repositories were affiliated with the EOSC. Of the 39 survey respondents, 23% (n=9) affiliated the EOSC Federation through Nodes (Candidate Nodes), 21% (n=8) managed by EOSC Association Members, and 8% (n=3) managed by Mandated Organisations. Two repositories held multiple affiliations, yielding 46% (n=18) with any formal EOSC affiliation and 54% (n=21) not.

2.2 Technical Infrastructure

2.2.1 General Metadata Practices

i. Metadata Standards Implementation

The vast majority of repositories (90%, n=35/39) indicated metadata sources beyond [DataCite](#) minimum requirements. Only 10% (n=4) relied exclusively on DataCite metadata schema, while 90% incorporated additional metadata standards, community schemas, or locally developed fields to enhance description and discoverability. This is illustrated in the figure below:

Figure 2: Distribution of responses to question about having sources of metadata beyond DataCite, segmented over

data repository size

Among repositories using DataCite exclusively, smaller data repositories hosting fewer than 100 datasets were overrepresented: 33% of repositories in this size category (n=3/9) indicated DataCite-only metadata. In contrast, among repositories hosting 100 or more datasets, only 1 of 30 (3%) used DataCite metadata exclusively, representing a clear outlier pattern. Larger repositories showed more complex metadata ecosystems to serve diverse user communities and discovery services.

A large majority of data repositories (87%, n=34/39) provided at least one form of domain / community-specific (DCS) metadata, with 62% (n=24/39) providing at least two. The survey distinguished four DCS metadata categories (non-mutually exclusive):

- Depositor-generated DCS metadata: 64% (n=25/39)
- Repository-generated DCS metadata: 62% (n=24/39)
- Curator-enriched DCS metadata: 49% (n=19/39)
- Other DCS metadata types: reported by multiple repositories

Amongst the data repositories that do not support any of these types of metadata, smaller repositories are somewhat overrepresented. However, even in this group, support for DCS metadata remained common: Amongst data repositories that host 100 datasets or less, 66% (n=6/9) indicated providing at least one DCS metadata type, compared to 87% across all repository sizes.

Free-text responses clarified that "Other" DCS metadata could consist of metadata imported or added through interactions between repository managers and researchers, representing collaborative curation processes that did not fit neatly into the depositor/repository/curator categories. These include DDI ([Data Documentation Initiative](#)) and [DataVerse](#) ("[which] offers some domain-specific metadata blocks") and an example on how data repositories could organise domain-specific metadata schemas provided by the concept of 'communities' in [B2Share](#).

Figure 3: Distribution of responses to question about providing domain/community-specific metadata and the exact Domain/Community-Specific Metadata Types

Analysis of raw responses revealed two distinct response types: **approximately half referenced metadata schemas** (DCAT, Dublin Core, DDI, discipline-specific schemas), **while the other half referenced representation formats** (XML, JSON, JSON-LD) **or data containers** (RO-Crate). This response heterogeneity complicated categorisation and may have affected reported adoption rates. Despite this interpretation complexity, clear patterns emerged: **Nearly all data repositories (97%, n=38/39) reported to offer metadata in a standardised way.** In fact, only 2 out of 39 respondents indicated that their data repository did not follow any standards.¹ Generic standards (e.g., Dublin Core, embedded metadata standards) were used by 76% (n=30/39), while community-specific standards were employed by 59% (n=23/39). Notably, 39% (n=15/39) used both generic and community-specific standards simultaneously.

¹ We acknowledge the discrepancy between these two statements. This can be traced back to one individual who selected "No standards are followed" as well as "Generic Standards" and "Community-specific standards" in their response to question 11. We attribute this inconsistency to a misunderstanding of how the options were presented in question 11. We also note that this discrepancy does not affect the conclusions in any substantial way.

Term	Count
Dublin Core	14
DataCite	13
DDI	11
JSON-LD	10
Schema.org	5
DCAT	4
JSON	3
Meta-Share	3
OAI-ORE	3
OpenAIRE	3
BibTeX	2
Darwin Core	2
ISO 19115/19139	2
METS	2
OAI-PMH	2
PREMIS	2
RO-Crate	2

Do you offer metadata in a standardised way? (N=39)

Figure 4: Venn diagram showing the overlap and complementarity of data repositories with DCS and generic standards

Open-ended responses identifying specific standards were structured through term extraction, normalisation, and generalisation (e.g., using "DDI" instead of "DDI Codebook," "DCAT" instead of "HealthDCAT-AP"). This process yielded 46 unique metadata standard terms across all responses. Standards mentioned shows how often specific terms were included in the responses, as may be seen in the below table:

[Q11] Do you offer metadata in a standardised way?
(N = 39)

Figure 5: Metadata standards and representation formats

Nearly all repositories (92%, n=36/39) made metadata discoverable to search engines through sitemaps, structured markup, or API access. Specifically, 74% (n=29/39) indicated that their resource metadata is accessible from the landing page of a resource through automated means such as Signposting (the [technology recommendation](#) of the previous TF on FAIR Metrics and Data Quality), or content negotiation (more ambiguity than Signposting). The remainder of respondents acknowledge that some of the metadata can only be retrieved through prior knowledge, or by looking at the resource documentation, indicating barriers to fully automated discovery. Only 8% (n=3) did not implement search engine discoverability mechanisms at all.

Three-quarters of repositories (74%, n=29/39) actively shared metadata with aggregation services, while 26% (n=10) did not participate in metadata aggregation. Aggregation partnerships supported broader discovery through services like OpenAIRE, DataCite, Google Dataset Search, and discipline-specific indexes, such as [DARIAH](#) and NOMAD.

[Q5 × Q13]

Q5: What is the type of your repository?

Q13: Does your repository provide an unambiguous way to find Digital Object-specific or domain-specific metadata document(s) (e.g. from the depositor or curator, and related to the content of the data)?

(N = 39)

Figure 6: Repository Type vs Metadata Sharing Practices. On the Y axis the answers for Q5 are shown.

Repository type analysis showed variation in metadata sharing practices. Generalist repositories demonstrated higher aggregation rates (86%, n=6/7) compared to discipline-specific repositories (69%, n=11/16) and institutional repositories (75%, n=6/8).

File-level metadata provision was reported by 59% of repositories (n=23/39), while 41% (n=16/39) did not provide metadata at file level. Among repositories providing file-level metadata, 49% of all repositories (n=19/39) made this metadata machine-discoverable, and 44% (n=17/39) implemented machine-actionable formats. This represented a 15-point gap between file-level provision (59%) and machine-actionable implementation (44%).

Documentation practices varied across the sample. The majority of repositories (72%, n=28/39) provided publicly available schema documentation, while 28% (n=11/39) did not document their metadata schemas publicly. Documentation typically took the form of online guides, technical specifications, or examples demonstrating metadata field usage.

Implementation of metadata field constraints showed diverse patterns. Repositories employed mandatory fields (85%, n=33/39), controlled vocabularies (72%, n=28/39), validation

rules (59%, n=23/39), and recommended fields (51%, n=20/39). Most repositories implemented multiple constraint types simultaneously to ensure metadata quality through complementary mechanisms—combining field requirements with vocabulary control and validation checking.

Fewer than one-third of repositories (31%, n=12/39) mapped all metadata fields to ontologies or controlled vocabularies. The majority (69%, n=27/39) either implemented partial mapping (mapping only selected high-priority fields) or no formal ontology alignment, limiting semantic interoperability potential and automated reasoning capabilities across repository boundaries.

ii. Metadata Validation Practices

Metadata validation made a distinction between repositories with systematic quality control from those without quality control mechanisms. This subsection examined validation adoption rates and the specific standards repositories validated against, demonstrating operational consistency between metadata implementation (Section 2.1.1) and quality assurance practices.

Metadata validation was implemented by 90% of repositories (n=35/39), inferred from provision of validation standards lists. The remaining 10% (n=4/39) did not provide validation standards.

Standards validated against closely matched standards implemented for metadata provision. DataCite emerged as the most common validation target at 20% of validating repositories (n=7/35), consistent with its dual role as baseline infrastructure and validation standard. Other frequently validated standards included Dublin Core, DDI (Data Documentation Initiative), and discipline-specific schemas (CMDI, REMBI, HL7 FHIR, NOMAD) mirroring the implementation patterns documented in Q11.

The 35 validating repositories collectively mentioned 65 distinct standard terms. This heterogeneity paralleled the 46 unique standards identified, demonstrating that repositories validated against the same diverse standards they implemented. The overlap between implementation and validation standards indicated operational consistency: repositories checked metadata quality against the standards they claimed to support.

iii. Metadata Harvesting and Updates

Most repositories (85%, n=33/39) supported OAI-PMH harvesting protocol, enabling metadata sharing with aggregators and discovery services through this widely-adopted standard.

Metadata update patterns varied substantially across the sample. Real-time or continuous updates were implemented by 46% (n=18/39), weekly updates by 18% (n=7/39), monthly updates by 15% (n=6/39), irregular updates by 13% (n=5/39), and daily updates by 8% (n=3/39). Update frequency varied across repository sizes: larger repositories more commonly implemented real-time updating while smaller repositories used scheduled batches or manual updates.

2.2.2 Licensing of Data and Metadata

The survey administered parallel questions about licensing practices for data and metadata, enabling systematic comparison across the same dimensions.

Dimension	Data Licensing	Metadata Licensing
Standards Compliance (e.g. SPDX, GUID, etc.)	54% (n=21/39) used standard identifiers	56.4% (n=22/39) used standards like SPDX
Machine-Readable Formats or with a shared commonly-understood identifier	64% (n=25/39) implemented SPDX or similar	Minimal
License Types - Creative Commons	85% (n=33/39)	Dominant
Granularity: Dataset-Level	87% (n=34/39)	33% (n=13/39) metadata-specific licenses
Machine-Actionable Semantic Web Standards (e.g. ODRL, ccREL)	Zero adoption reported	Zero adoption reported

Table 1: Comparative overview of data and metadata licensing practices across surveyed repositories.

Three systematic implementation gaps emerged from the data-metadata comparison. For data licensing, a 29-point gap separated machine-readable discoverability (92%, n=36/39) from machine-actionability (64%, n=25/39), while granularity showed an even larger 51-point gap between dataset-level (87%, n=34/39) and file-level (36%, n=14/39) application. Metadata licensing showed similar patterns but with more limited machine-actionable implementation: only 2-3 repositories used standards, despite 56% claiming standards compliance.

Similarities across data and metadata contexts revealed consistent patterns in repository licensing approaches. Standards compliance reached moderate levels in both contexts (data 54%, metadata 56%), yet machine-actionable implementation significantly lagged human-readable approaches in both cases. Creative Commons licenses dominated across both data and metadata contexts. Most notably, zero repositories reported adopting semantic web standards (e.g. ODRL, ccREL) designed explicitly for machine-actionable rights expression, representing a systematic gap.

Differences between data and metadata licensing reflect measurement scope and operational priorities. Data licensing was measured more systematically across multiple dimensions including requirements, discoverability, and machine-actionability, while metadata questions focused more narrowly on standards compliance and contractual mechanisms. Granularity assessment was conducted for data (dataset vs file vs metadata levels) while metadata licensing showed some

additional mechanisms not measured for data: 44% (n=16/36) of repositories used contracts beyond standard licenses and 5% (n=2/39) employed in-house vocabularies.

i. Questions Asked Only for Data Licensing:

Data-specific questions assessed dimensions not measured for metadata. License requirements were nearly universal, with 92% (n=36/39) of repositories requiring licenses for data access and reuse while only 8% (n=3/39) did not implement such requirements. Human-readable discoverability matched this level at 92% (n=36/39) making licenses discoverable to users, while machine-discoverability through distinct metadata fields reached 79% (n=31/39).

License type diversity was examined exclusively for data, revealing Creative Commons dominance at 85% (n=33/39) alongside custom licenses at 41% (n=16/39), open government licenses at 28% (n=11/39), and other types at 23% (n=9/39). File-level licensing was implemented by 36% (n=14/39) of repositories. One question on modification rights received insufficient response for analysis, with only 8% response rate (n=3/39), likely reflecting narrow applicability to repositories with specific modification workflows rather than universal relevance.

ii: Questions Asked Only for Metadata Licensing:

Metadata-specific questions focused on technical implementation details and contractual mechanisms. Among repositories using standards for metadata licensing (n=22), universal GUID usage was high at 86% (n=19/22), indicating that repositories adopting standards generally employed commonly recognized license URIs. In-house controlled vocabularies remained rare at 5% (n=2/39), with 95% (n=37/39) relying on standard options. Additional contractual mechanisms beyond standard licenses were applied by 44% (n=16/36), while 56% (n=20/36) relied solely on standard licenses. Question 36 assessed whether repositories differentiated licenses by metadata type (curated versus deposited, fully-open versus authenticated access), addressing granular rights expression for heterogeneous metadata contexts.

[Q22 × Q27]

Q22: Is the license machine-discoverable? (There is a distinct metadata field in the record-level metadata related to license)

Q27: Is the license machine-actionable?

(N = 39)

Figure 7: Distribution of responses between machine-discoverable and machine-actionable licenses

Repository type influenced machine-actionable licensing implementation. Institutional repositories showed higher adoption of machine-actionable data licensing formats at 75% (n=6/8) compared to discipline-specific repositories at 56% (n=9/16).

Notably, only 3 repositories (8% response rate) provided information about license modification rights. Given the limited response, no generalisable conclusions can be drawn for this question.

2.2.3 Persistent Identifiers

Questions examined persistent identifier implementation at dataset and file levels, enabling comparison of universal dataset-level adoption against variability in granular file-level identification.

i. Dataset-Level PID Implementation

All repositories (100%, n=39/39) assigned persistent identifiers at dataset level.

DOI was the dominant persistent identifier type, used by 97% of repositories (n=38/39). Other PID types showed substantially lower adoption: Handle (26%, n=10/39), ARK (13%, n=5/39), URN (10%, n=4/39), and locally-developed identifiers (8%, n=3/39). Multiple PID systems were sometimes implemented in parallel, particularly in repositories supporting legacy identifier schemes alongside DOI or serving specialised communities with PID type preferences.

DataCite infrastructure was used by 68% of repositories (n=26/39) for DOI registration and metadata services. The remaining 32% (n=13/39) used alternative PID infrastructure (primarily Handle.net for Handle PIDs) or managed identifier services independently through local resolver implementations.

ii. File-Level PID Implementation

Persistent identifier implementation at file level showed substantially lower adoption than dataset level. File-level PID provision was reported by 59% (n=23/39), while 41% (n=16/39) did not assign PIDs to individual files within datasets. Among repositories providing file-level PIDs, machine-discoverability was implemented by 54% (n=21/39), and machine-actionable formats by 51% (n=20/39). This created a 49-point gap between dataset-level (100%) and file-level (51%) machine-actionable PID implementation. Strictly speaking, repositories that implement Signposting do not need to generate PIDs for their data records - unambiguous identification arises from the explicit pointer and resolution mechanism in the Signposting metadata. Given that repository software such as Dataverse already implement at least the FAIR Signposting subset of the larger Signposting specification, this may account for at least some of this discrepancy.

Among the 23 repositories reporting file-level PID assignment, responses about specific PID types used indicated: DOIs (n=3 mentions), Handle PIDs (n=2 mentions), and ARK (n=1 mention). Several responses described internal identifier schemes specific to repository platforms: "NOMAD assigns externally facing identifiers to the entries within a deposit," "all metadata will be assigned with IDs," "to each file," "to each object." One repository noted they "sometimes" assign file-level PIDs but "don't have PIDs for files" systematically, while another indicated that file-level PIDs "will be available in the new version of the website" but were not currently implemented, both reflecting transitional states in infrastructure development.

2.3 Operational Practices

2.3.1 Provenance and Contextual Information

Provenance tracking is widely practiced, but primarily through internal, non-standard mechanisms rather than recognised community standards. Nearly 90% of repositories surveyed (n=35/39) indicated they tracked provenance in some form (either standard or non-standard). This confirmed that provenance was considered necessary across repositories.

Most repositories (72%, n=28/39) include local, non-standard solutions to record provenance (e.g., custom metadata fields, repository-specific logs, or internal workflows). In comparison, 18% of repositories (n=7/39) used standard vocabularies like [W3C PROV-O](#), DataCite, or related frameworks.

Additionally, 10% of repositories (n=4/39) did not track provenance at all. Hence, although most repositories handled provenance tracking, the ecosystem was fragmented. The reliance on internal methods, combined with low adoption of standards, leads to interoperability issues, difficulty exchanging provenance information across platforms, and problems with automated harvesting and reuse.

Respondents most commonly reported making provenance information available through metadata fields (63%, n=25/39) and dataset landing pages (23%, n=9/39). Only a minority provided machine-actionable access (9% made it accessible via API, n=3/39, and 9% via downloadable files, n=3/39), and almost none mentioned relying on standardised provenance dissemination mechanisms. Also, one of the repositories indicated that provenance existed internally but was not (yet) publicly or systematically exposed.

The responses show that almost all repositories provide multiple forms of contextual information. Only one respondent indicated otherwise. Out of the 39 repositories surveyed, 82% (n=32/39) supplied clear licensing and access information, 59% (n=23/39) provided version histories, audit trails, or changelogs, and almost half of the repositories (46–49%) provided other rich technical and methodological context like data dictionaries/codebooks (49%, n=19/39), software/tools information (46%, n=18/39), experimental methods or data-collection protocols (46%, n=18/39), and quality assurance/validation procedures (46%, n=18/39).

Figure 8: Repository Validated standards

The responses show that a majority of repositories provide provenance information in machine-readable form, but the ecosystem remains fragmented. In particular, 62% of the repositories that filled in the survey (n=24/39) reported that provenance/context information was captured in a structured, machine-readable format (e.g., JSON, XML, RDF, or standardized metadata fields), while 38% (n=15/39) still relied on human-readable or informal approaches, e.g., textual descriptions in landing pages or non-standard internal systems. Hence, as almost 40% of repositories still lacked this capability, this limits cross-repository interoperability, automated harvesting, and alignment with FAIR and EOSC expectations.

There is a clear dominance (64%) of JSON as the format for representing machine-readable provenance/context information. In contrast, a relatively low percentage of repositories adopted more formal or FAIR-aligned approaches, such as RDF (26%) or RO-Crate (8%).

The responses show that most of the surveyed repositories (almost 70%, n=27/39) support linking datasets to related research outputs (publications, code, protocols, software, workflows). However, a significant minority (30%, n=12/39) still did not support such linking, indicating a potential interoperability and FAIR maturity gap that constrains the full integration of datasets within the broader research lifecycle and the EOSC ecosystem.

2.3.2 FAIR Metrics

Q51: Is it possible/required for data users to give back enriched versions of a dataset?
(N = 39)

Figure 9: FAIR Reusability for Metadata Enrichment

Slightly more than half (51%, n=20/39) reported assessing FAIR metrics related to reusability, while 49% (n=19/39) did not conduct such assessments.

Systematic approaches to assess FAIRness: 36% (n=14/39). No systematic methods: 38% (n=15/39). Partial implementation: 26% (n=10/39).

[Q51 × Q53]

Q51: Is it possible/required for data users to give back enriched versions of a dataset?

Q53: Do you currently assess any FAIR metrics related to reusability (e.g., licensing clarity, metadata richness, provenance, interoperability)?

(N = 39)

Figure 10: FAIR Assessment Adoption and Systematic Methods

Among the 21 repository managers responded providing specifics, reported approaches included metadata richness evaluation using [F-UJI](#) (mentioned by multiple repositories), manual metadata quality checks, community-specific metadata validation, licensing clarity assessment, format compliance verification, and curation processes. Multiple repositories focused on specific FAIR dimensions (particularly metadata quality and licensing) rather than comprehensive assessment across all four principles.

2.4 Policy and Governance

Nearly all repositories (95%, n=37/39) had documented policies governing data management, preservation, and access. Only 5% (n=2/39) operated without formal policy documentation. Repositories implemented diverse policy types, with data preservation policies most common (87%, n=34/39), followed by data access policies (85%, n=33/39), data submission policies (77%, n=30/39), metadata quality policies (69%, n=27/39), and license policies (64%, n=25/39). Most repositories maintained multiple policy types covering different operational aspects.

Q61: Does the repository have any of these types of policies?
(N = 39)

Figure 11 : Repository policies

Policy machine-readability shows minimal adoption. Only 11% of repositories (n=4/39) made policies available in machine-readable formats, while 89% (n=35/39) maintained policies as human-readable documents only. Among repositories with machine-readable policies, 8% (n=3/39) made them machine-discoverable, and 8% (n=3/39) implemented machine-actionable policy formats.

Policy embedding of FAIR principles was reported by 74% (n=29/39), while 26% (n=10/39) did not explicitly incorporate FAIR principles into policy frameworks. However, machine-discoverable FAIR policy statements existed in only 21% (n=8/39), and machine-actionable FAIR policies in just 13% (n=5/39).

[Q62 × Q66]

Q62: Are those policies machine-readable or exposed in metadata (e.g., schema.org, via registration in FAIRsharing)?

Q66: What type of organisation/entity is this?

(N = 12)

Figure 12: Policy Implementation Gap: Adoption vs Machine-Readability

Only around 30% of surveyed repositories (n=12/39) reviewed or curated their data entries after specific time intervals, with frequency ranging from monthly to every 5 years; however, the majority did not specify any time frame. For over two-thirds of the repositories (69%, n=27/39), data records were not reviewed after a specific time. However, it should be noted that some repositories curated and reviewed all entries upon deposition, which was reflected in both answer possibilities.

The majority of repositories (69%, n=27/39) were independently operated, while another organisation or entity managed 31% (n=12/39). Among those, half of the respondents (n=6/12) reported that the managing entity was a university or research-performing organisation. Two respondents (16.6%) indicated that a private company ran their repositories, and one respondent (8%) stated that a government body managed it. The remaining 25% (n=3/12) indicated various other arrangements, most frequently describing their repositories as being operated by research networks.

2.5 Sustainability

The vast majority of surveyed repositories provided user training and support (85%, n=33/39) and implemented shared responsibility for repository development and maintenance through community involvement (80%, n=31/39) and collaborations (77%, n=30/39). Over two-thirds employed data preservation strategies (69%, n=27/39) and were built on long-term funding (67%, n=26/39). Additionally, 62% (n=24/39) engaged in open-access initiatives. Over half of the surveyed repositories (51%, n=20/39) underwent regular audits and evaluations.

Figure 13: Sustainability measures applied by repositories

2.6 EOSC Federation Alignment

None of the respondents fundamentally rejected the principles of the EOSC Federation model. Furthermore, given that 38% (n=15/39) of the participants fully agreed with the principles and 41% (n=16/39) agreed with them at least in part, a large proportion of respondents (combined 78%, n=30/39) accepted the EOSC Federation Handbook.

Although none of the reactions rejected the objectives of the EOSC Federation and many even expressed their support, the answers pointed to relevant **challenges in implementation, which could be categorised into four groups:**

a) Resources:

- Lack of financial and human resources
- Lack of support in establishing connectivity between local and federated services

b) Technology:

- Technical challenges in achieving interoperability
- Semantic challenges for establishing interoperability

c) Organisation:

- Policy-related and coordination aspects
- Lack of a clear mandate and governance

d) Community:

- High complexity makes it difficult for users and providers to understand the details of the EOSC Federation
- Lack of maturity is an obstacle for some communities
- Lack of focus on showing real tangible benefits for researchers
- Support needs showed convergence around three areas: funding (74%, n=29/39), technical guidance (74%, n=29/39), and community building (59%, n=23/39).

Q70: What kind of support would help you better align with EOSC initiatives and policies?
(N = 39)

Figure 14: Support Needs Identified by Repositories

3. Discussion

The survey results confirm a consistent pattern across the European repositories who replied to the survey: solid adoption of machine-readable FAIR infrastructure but limited progress toward machine-actionable capabilities. Persistent identifiers, license requirements, and metadata sharing are now standard practice, yet automation and semantic interoperability remain constrained. This highlights the need to evolve from descriptive FAIRness toward computable, policy-aware, and provenance-enabled FAIRness, precisely the direction defined by ongoing EOSC initiatives such as OSTRails and FIDELIS. However, the relative magnitude of the quantified gaps should be interpreted with caution, as their practical impact on EOSC Federation readiness depends on contextual factors such as disciplinary sensitivity, repository scale, and the specific automation requirements of EOSC services. Furthermore, as the sample was drawn through convenience sampling rather than a probability-based frame, findings should be interpreted as indicative of this cohort rather than generalised to the European repository landscape as a whole.

3.1 FAIR Implementation: Infrastructure and Standardisation Gaps

Four core capability gaps structure the results:

1. **Provenance interoperability** (54-point gap): A 54-point provenance gap separated repositories tracking data lineage internally (72%, n=28/39) from those using standard vocabularies enabling cross-repository interoperability (18%, n=7/39). Most repositories captured provenance through diverse mechanisms—version control systems, metadata fields, audit logs, repository-specific workflows—but these proprietary approaches limited automated provenance reasoning across repository boundaries. Only 13% (n=5/39) implemented machine-actionable standard vocabularies (W3C PROV-O, DataCite provenance extensions, RO-Crate), constraining repositories' ability to participate in federated provenance graphs linking datasets to their generation processes, transformation pipelines, and derivative works. The gap reflected repositories treating provenance as internal record-keeping rather than as federated infrastructure enabling downstream reusers to computationally verify data quality and appropriateness for specific analytical contexts.
2. **PID granularity** (49-point gap): The 49-point PID gap distinguishes universal dataset-level persistent identifier adoption (100%, n=39/39) from inconsistent file-level implementation (51%, n=20/39 machine-actionable). DOI dominance was near-universal (97%, n=38/39), establishing citation infrastructure for primary research objects. However, granular identification enabling precise reference to dataset components—individual files, specific data subsets, particular analysis results—remained inconsistent. Among repositories providing file-level PIDs (59%, n=23/39), actual machine-actionable formats reached only 51%. Task Force members noted that repositories implementing Signposting (an alternative approach using typed links to provide pointers from dataset landing pages to files) may not require separate file-level PIDs while achieving similar discoverability, suggesting the gap may overstate limitations for repositories using link-based navigation rather than minting distinct identifiers for each component.
3. **Licensing actionability** (28-point gap): The 29-point licensing gap separated repositories making licenses discoverable to humans (92%, n=36/39) from those implementing machine-actionable formats enabling automated rights reasoning (64%, n=25/39). While Creative Commons dominated (85%, n=33/39 for data licensing), no repositories reported using ODRL (Open Digital Rights Language) or ccREL—semantic web standards designed explicitly for computationally interpretable rights expression. This zero adoption suggests a very limited adoption of machine-actionable rights frameworks, despite their centrality to the FAIR Metrics Task Force's emphasis on "specification for machine-actionable data usage policies." Furthermore, licensing showed substantial granularity gaps: dataset-level application reached 87% (n=34/39) while file-level licensing remained at 36% (n=14/39)—a 51-point disparity limiting repositories' ability to express heterogeneous rights within collections containing both open data and access-restricted components.
4. **Policy machine-readability** (84-point gap): The 84-point policy gap between formal policy adoption (95%, n=37/39) and machine-readable formats (11%, n=4/39) represented the largest observed disparity. Nearly all repositories maintained formal policies governing data operations—preservation policies (87%), access policies (85%), submission policies (77%)—yet these remained primarily human-readable documents rather than machine-actionable metadata enabling automated compliance checking. Even among repositories embedding FAIR principles in policies (74%, n=29/39), machine-actionable FAIR policy statements were implemented by only 13% (n=5/39), representing a 61-point gap.

Repository data curation practices showed limited systematic review: only 30% (n=12/39) reviewed data entries on scheduled intervals (monthly to every 5 years), while 69% (n=27/39) did not implement time-based review cycles. Some repositories reviewed all entries upon deposition, suggesting event-driven rather than schedule-driven curation. The limited scheduled review combined with low policy machine-readability (11%) suggests repositories lack automated governance systems flagging datasets requiring re-evaluation for compliance verification, rights clearance renewal, or quality re-assessment—exactly the capability machine-actionable policies would enable.

Together, these illustrate the start of a transition phase where repositories are supporting FAIR publishing strongly at the deposit metadata level, but have not yet implemented comprehensive support that would facilitate accurate data discovery and reuse - a key objective for EOSC.

3.1.1 Metadata Standards Heterogeneity and the Schema-Format Conflation Problem

Responses revealed high variability in metadata practices: 46 distinct standards and formats were reported, ranging from generic schemas (Dublin Core, DCAT, DataCite) to community-specific ones (DDI, CMDI, HL7 FHIR). Critically, many repositories conflated different layers of standardisation including but not limited to, **metadata schemas** (semantic models defining field meaning and structure), **serialisation formats** (syntactic encodings such as XML and JSON), and **packaging containers** (structured formats bundling data and metadata together, such as RO-Crate), treating them as interchangeable 'metadata standards'. JSON-LD spans both the serialisation and semantic layers, which further contributed to inconsistent categorisation across respondents.

This confusion explains much of the interoperability gap: while 97% of repositories use at least one standard, only 31% map all fields to ontologies that enable automated reasoning. The 90% that perform validation often do so syntactically rather than semantically, limiting cross-repository interoperability.

The OSTrails FAIR Interoperability Framework (FAIR-IF) directly addresses this issue, which distinguishes these layers, as well as the type of standards (using of [FAIRsharing](#)), and defines how metadata, provenance, and licenses should be represented consistently across repositories. This approach provides the practical blueprint needed to move from diverse metadata usage toward coherent, machine-actionable FAIRness.

Future surveys should distinguish validation mechanisms to assess infrastructure maturity and federation readiness, as automated validation infrastructure proves essential for repositories processing high submission volumes or participating in real-time federation services requiring immediate compliance verification.

3.1.2 FAIR Assessment Fragmentation and the Measurement Rigor Gap

Just over half of repositories (51%) report conducting FAIR assessments, yet only one-third apply systematic methodologies. The remainder perform partial or ad hoc checks focused on single FAIR dimensions such as metadata quality or licensing. This inconsistency reflects a fragmented landscape of FAIR evaluation, with limited comparability across tools and domains.

The absence of standardised output structures prevents automated benchmarking or integration of FAIR results across systems. The [OSTrails FAIRness Reference Model](#) addresses this fragmentation by defining a common data structure – the FAIR Test Result Set – that standardises how assessment tools express outcomes, enabling direct comparison and machine-actionable reuse of FAIR evaluations.

3.1.3 File-Level Metadata: Aspiration-Reality Gap

While 59% of repositories report providing file-level metadata, only 44% expose it in machine-actionable formats. Many consider README files or textual descriptions sufficient, reflecting inconsistent interpretations of “file-level metadata”. This ambiguity limits automated verification of file formats, dependencies, and processing requirements.

The findings underline the need for clearer operational definitions and standardised mechanisms to ensure that object-level metadata can be automatically interpreted and linked within federated workflows. For instance, Signposting offers one practical pathway: by embedding typed HTTP link headers on dataset landing pages, it enables automated agents to navigate directly to metadata documents, content files, and related resources without prior knowledge of the repository's structure. Complementarily, FAIR-IF schema extensions define how object-level metadata should be expressed consistently – specifying which fields, vocabularies, and formats federated services can rely on for automated interpretation and cross-repository comparison.

3.1.4 Repository Heterogeneity and Typological Patterns

FAIR implementation varies by repository type and size. Generalist repositories exhibit higher aggregation rates and broader standards adoption, while discipline-specific and institutional repositories show deeper but narrower metadata practices tailored to community norms. Smaller repositories more often rely solely on DataCite metadata, whereas larger ones deploy multiple schemas and validation mechanisms.

This diversity reflects legitimate differences in disciplinary requirements rather than inconsistency. The FAIR-IF accommodates such heterogeneity by defining a common interoperability baseline while allowing domain-specific extensions. This ensures that repositories can remain context-appropriate yet interoperable within the EOSC Federation.

3.2 EOSC Federation: Current State and Way Forward

The findings confirm a clear distinction between **FAIR-enabled discovery and federation-ready reusability**. Repositories largely support machine-readable discovery mechanisms (identifiers, landing pages, metadata sharing), but federation services require machine-actionable implementations to automate reuse decisions across systems.

This evidence aligns with the Task Force's focus from repository-focused FAIRness toward data-level reusability metrics, where services must be able to automatically interpret rights, provenance, policy constraints, and object granularity. In practice, the main blockers for repositories are not conceptual alignment with EOSC, but missing interoperability mechanisms that allow FAIR information to be computed and compared across heterogeneous infrastructures.

These challenges are being actively addressed across a growing portfolio of Horizon Europe EOSC projects, including coordination and EOSC Federation initiatives alongside domain-specific implementation efforts. Beyond technical specification gaps, the adoption of machine-actionable FAIR practices will likely depend on incentive structures and recognition mechanisms, including clearly defined interoperability tiers and potential certification pathways that reward repositories for progressing toward higher levels of federation readiness. In this context, existing repository trustworthiness frameworks such as the CoreTrustSeal certification (CTS), aligned with broader principles of trustworthy digital repositories (Lin et al., 2020), may provide a complementary baseline for organisational reliability, alongside FAIR maturity indicators focused on interoperability and machine-actionability.

Although most repositories endorse EOSC Federation principles, systematic FAIR assessment remains uneven. This **gap between stated alignment and operational implementation** reflects the real-world barriers repositories face – technical complexity, limited interoperability mechanisms, insufficient guidelines, and constrained funding – rather than any absence of willingness. The strongest signals from respondents point to practical needs: technical guidance, funding, and community coordination.

3.2.1 EOSC Candidate Nodes, Members and Mandated Organisations Insights

The survey captured repositories with diverse EOSC Federation affiliations, providing insight into technical capabilities across different organizational relationships to the Federation. Of the 39 respondents, 46% (n=18/39) maintained formal affiliation with EOSC through one or more of three mechanisms: Selected Node designation, EOSC Association membership, or Mandated Organization status. The remaining 54% (n=21/39) operated independently of formal EOSC structures while potentially participating in EOSC-related projects or initiatives.

Selected Node repositories demonstrated higher adoption of file-level persistent identifiers compared to non-affiliated repositories: 50% (n=3/6 excluding overlaps with Members/MOs) versus 30% (n=10/33 for repositories without Selected Node affiliation): a 20-percentage-point advantage suggesting these repositories prioritised granular identification enabling precise component reference essential for federation services. However, machine-actionable licensing showed comparable implementation across all affiliation types: 83% (n=5/6) for Selected Nodes versus 85% (n=28/33) for other repositories, indicating this capability achieved broad adoption across the European repository landscape regardless of formal EOSC affiliation status.

Across affiliation types, capability differences appear incremental rather than structural. Several federation-relevant practices extend beyond formally affiliated nodes, suggesting that readiness is distributed across the wider repository landscape. Where gaps persist (notably object granularity and interoperable provenance/policy expression), targeted support should focus on implementing shared interoperability patterns—not on organisational status. Approaches such as Signposting can also provide practical pathways toward federation integration where file-level PID minting is not feasible.

3.2.2 Initiatives Addressing Identified Gaps

The capability gaps identified here are already being addressed through coordinated EOSC efforts

that combine assessment harmonisation, technical interoperability specifications, and repository capacity building. The Task Force’s outputs support comparability and uptake of FAIR assessment and discovery practices, while OSTrails (FAIR-IF and the FAIRness Reference Model) provides the interoperability layer for machine-actionable FAIR evaluations. FIDELIS complements this with the organisational and network foundations required to sustain implementation over time.

The following table summarises how these initiatives contribute to FAIR metrics implementation and EOSC Federation readiness.

<p>OSTrails Project: Technical Specifications Addressing Measured Gaps</p>	<p>The OSTrails FAIR Interoperability Framework (FAIR-IF) and FAIRness Reference Model directly address the gaps identified in this study, providing a technical and conceptual foundation for machine-actionable FAIR implementation across repositories, DMP tools, and knowledge graphs.</p> <p>The FAIRness Reference Model (OSTrails D1.2) defines a common structure – the <i>FAIR Test Result Set</i> – to standardize outputs of FAIR assessment tools. This resolves the current fragmentation, where over half of repositories report assessing FAIRness but only one-third use systematic approaches. By harmonizing how assessment tools express results, the model enables repositories, DMP systems, and federation services to automatically exchange and compare FAIR evaluations.</p> <p>The FAIR-IF translates these principles into technical specifications that make FAIR assessments interoperable and machine-actionable. It introduces FAIR Implementation Profiles (FIPs) that clearly distinguish between semantic, structural, syntactic, and protocol layers – addressing the “schema-format conflation problem” observed in our survey. Through these profiles, repositories can align metadata standards, provenance models, and licensing structures without redundancy, enabling automated reasoning and reuse across systems.</p> <p>Together, the FAIR-IF and the FAIRness Reference Model operationalize the shift from FAIR <i>assessment</i> to FAIR <i>implementation</i>: they provide the missing technical layer connecting FAIR evaluation to automated EOSC federation services.</p>
<p>FIDELIS: Repository Trustworthiness and Network Development</p>	<p>The FIDELIS project (Establishing a European Network of Trustworthy Digital Repositories) complements FAIR implementation efforts through focus on repository trustworthiness, support infrastructure, and network building.</p>

	<p>FIDELIS conducted landscape survey analysis (Milestone M11/M19, June 2025, DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15744996) assessing current practices, challenges, and support needs across European repositories, providing complementary perspective to our FAIR-focused technical capability assessment. Where our survey quantified machine-actionable infrastructure gaps, FIDELIS examined trustworthiness frameworks, legal challenges, training needs, and community support mechanisms enabling sustained repository operations beyond technical implementation.</p> <p>FIDELIS addresses the organizational sustainability dimensions our Section 5 findings revealed: repositories with long-term funding (67%), user training programs (85%), and community involvement (80%) demonstrated higher capacity for machine-actionable infrastructure maintenance requiring ongoing technical staff and standards evolution tracking.</p>
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Together, OSTRails and FIDELIS define complementary pathways toward EOSC Federation readiness: OSTRails standardises FAIR data interoperability, while FIDELIS enables repositories to remain trusted, resilient, and capable of maintaining those standards over time.

3.2.3 Sustainability Infrastructure and FAIR Capacity

Repository sustainability indicators suggest a solid foundation for sustained FAIR capability development. Most repositories provide user training and support (85%, n=33/39) and involve their communities in governance (80%, n=31/39). Over two-thirds report long-term funding (67%, n=26/39) and preservation strategies (69%, n=27/39), while half undergo regular audits or evaluations (51%, n=20/39). Together, these measures reflect organisational capacity to maintain infrastructure beyond initial implementation.

Sustainability also helps explain variation in machine-actionable readiness across repository types. Repositories with stronger institutional embedding and stable resources appear better positioned to maintain complex, evolving implementations (e.g., granular rights expression, interoperable provenance, and automated policy checks), while others may prioritise machine-readable formats that are easier to deploy and maintain. Standardised implementations require continued maintenance as vocabularies, profiles, and interoperability expectations evolve.

This highlights an important implication for Federation readiness: persistent endpoints, reliable identifier resolution, stable access mechanisms, and maintained provenance and rights information depend not only on technical choices but on ongoing organisational capacity. The strong convergence of support needs around funding (74%, n=29/39) and technical guidance (74.3%, n=29/39) reinforces that sustainability and expertise must be addressed together to enable progressive FAIR maturity. In this perspective, federation-readiness criteria may also need to be calibrated according to domain-specific risk profiles, as high-sensitivity or regulated data contexts may legitimately require stronger validation and certification mechanisms than fully open data environments.

3.3 Limitations

Several limitations constrain the generalisability and interpretation of these findings.

First, the survey reflects a European sample (39 repositories), shaped by European policy and infrastructure contexts (e.g., EOSC and Horizon Europe). Priorities, terminology, and implementation incentives may differ in other regions, limiting transferability to the global repository landscape.

Second, the study is cross-sectional: it captures repository capabilities during the 2025 data collection period and does not assess change over time. As a result, the analysis cannot determine whether gaps in machine-actionable FAIR implementation are narrowing, widening, or remaining stable.

Third, Task Force members noted occasional mismatches between reported practices and their experiences, which may reflect differences between policy and implementation, inconsistent interpretations of technical terms (e.g., “file-level metadata”), or social desirability bias. Future work should triangulate survey results with automated checks (e.g., endpoint testing and tool-based assessments) and targeted manual validation of repository implementations. Moreover, reported implementation should not be conflated with demonstrated operational capability: the presence of a declared standard or feature does not necessarily guarantee its completeness, maintenance status, semantic coherence, or effective integration into automated workflows. These gaps may also reflect heterogeneous contexts and interpretations of FAIR, in addition to implementation limitations.

Fourth, several open-ended questions required manual categorisation (e.g., metadata standards, provenance methods, EOSC barriers), introducing interpretive judgement and potential classification ambiguity. In addition, reported technologies may refer to heterogeneous layers (e.g., formats, metadata schemas, ontologies), which limits direct comparability across categories. Reliability would benefit from independent coding by multiple analysts and inter-rater agreement checks. The absence of formal inter-coder reliability assessment constitutes a methodological limitation, as categorisation and normalisation decisions may have influenced the aggregation of standards and the quantification of capability gaps. In addition, some questions had limited response rates (e.g., detailed FAIR assessment tooling), reducing confidence in those specific results.

Finally, subgroup sizes across repository types were uneven (e.g., institutional $n=8$; generalist $n=7$), limiting robustness of cross-tab comparisons. Observed differences by repository type should therefore be interpreted cautiously and validated through larger, more balanced samples.

Self-assessment bias and the need for robust FAIR quality thresholds

This study relies on self-reported information from repository managers, which introduces an intrinsic epistemic limitation. While respondents are generally knowledgeable about their infrastructures, the accuracy of FAIR-related self-assessments depends critically on the technical expertise, institutional role, and interpretative framework of the respondent. In several cases, Task Force members observed discrepancies between reported capabilities and their direct experience

with repository implementations.

This highlights an important meta-result of the survey: beyond measuring FAIR maturity itself, the study reveals that the veracity of FAIR assessment is strongly influenced by the skills and contextual understanding of respondents and stakeholders (David et al., 2020). Even when repositories believe they comply with a given FAIR requirement, the underlying implementation may not fully align with machine-actionable expectations.

Several examples illustrate this assessment paradox:

- **Ontology usage does not guarantee semantic interoperability.**
Repositories may report using a “standard ontology,” yet this may refer to outdated, partially implemented, locally adapted, or weakly governed versions. The quality, maintenance status, and semantic coherence of ontologies are rarely examined in self-assessments. Adoption of an ontology label does not necessarily imply effective interoperability.
- **Rich metadata cannot be fully evaluated automatically.**
Metadata richness and adequacy are highly context-dependent. Automated tools can verify structural completeness or syntactic compliance, but they cannot determine whether metadata are sufficient, relevant, or semantically appropriate for a given reuse scenario. Human expertise remains indispensable in assessing contextual fitness-for-purpose.
- **Minimum FAIR requirements require multi-layered validation:** FAIR compliance cannot rely solely on automated checks nor solely on self-declaration. Robust evaluation requires triangulation: automated FAIR assessment tools (e.g., F-UJI, FOOPs, FAIR Evaluator), independent technical verification, and qualitative expert review.

This limitation points to a broader strategic challenge for the EOSC Federation. FAIR is not binary; it is a continuum. Yet federation services will require operational thresholds: at what point is a dataset/repository sufficiently FAIR to be considered interoperable and reusable within EOSC workflows?

A critical future step for EOSC will therefore be to define how FAIR quality tiers or maturity levels should be structured. Acceptable FAIR levels must be specified dimension by dimension – and potentially sub-dimension by sub-dimension – distinguishing, for example, between human-readable compliance, machine-readable structuring, and machine-actionable semantic interoperability. Aggregate FAIR scores are insufficient; explicit criteria are needed to describe minimal, intermediate, and advanced states of implementation.

Equally important may be the question of which validation mechanisms provide the most robust certification of FAIR quality for each dimension. Different forms of control provide different strengths:

- Automated syntactic validation ensures structural compliance.
- Semantic validation (ontology alignment, vocabulary control) improves interoperability.
- Independent technical audits enhance reliability and comparability.
- Expert qualitative review evaluates contextual adequacy and disciplinary fitness-for-purpose.

The appropriate balance between these mechanisms may depend on context. High-sensitivity

domains (e.g., health data, high-containment biological infrastructures) may require stronger independent verification, while lower-risk open data contexts may rely more extensively on automated checks.

Defining explicit FAIR quality thresholds and context-sensitive validation frameworks will be essential if EOSC moves toward certification of Federation readiness. Without such calibration, FAIR will remain an aspirational guiding framework rather than a reliably operationalised basis for federation-level interoperability. Establishing clear, dimension-specific criteria for acceptable FAIR implementation will be a critical milestone in transitioning from voluntary alignment toward trusted, machine-actionable federation integration. It should be noted, however, that such thresholds and validation pathways do not yet exist as fixed EOSC baseline requirements – they remain part of an actively evolving implementation landscape, shaped by ongoing work across the Task Force, OSTRails, and the broader EOSC ecosystem.

4. Conclusions

This survey of 39 European research data repositories provides an empirical foundation for the ongoing evolution of FAIR assessment from repository-centric discovery metrics toward **data-level reusability evaluation**. The analysis suggests a dual-speed landscape: repositories have achieved near-universal adoption of human-readable FAIR infrastructure—identifiers, metadata, and licensing—yet remain limited in machine-actionable capabilities required for automated reuse. The magnitude of implementation gaps (28–84 points across policy, provenance, PID, and licensing dimensions) underscores that Europe’s repositories are *discoverable* but not yet *computable*.

Beyond infrastructure gaps, the study also highlights a methodological challenge: FAIR maturity is often self-assessed, yet its veracity depends on technical expertise, interpretative clarity, and validation mechanisms. As EOSC advances toward federation integration, defining explicit FAIR quality thresholds and robust, context-sensitive certification pathways will be essential to ensure that reported FAIRness corresponds to operational, machine-actionable reality.

These results support the EOSC FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force strategy and directly inform the **OStrails FAIR Interoperability Framework (FAIR-IF)** and **FAIRness Reference Model**, which together define how FAIR assessments can become interoperable and machine-actionable. The survey provides a quantitative baseline to inform evidence-based prioritisation of technical interventions as OStrails and related EOSC projects refine their specifications through pilot testing.

Significance for EOSC Federation Readiness

For the EOSC Federation Build-Up phase, these findings clarify the challenge: while repositories meet the prerequisites for discovery and aggregation, federation services require automated reasoning over rights, provenance, and policy information. The gap is not in willingness—78 % of repositories support the federation model—but in the absence of shared machine-actionable formats, guidelines and sustainable resources. Strong metadata aggregation and granular PID adoption provide a solid foundation for scaling to federation participation once automation and interoperability frameworks are implemented.

Cross-Project Coordination and Collaborative Development

The survey exemplifies effective coordination within the EOSC ecosystem. Its design and analysis involved collaboration between the FAIR Metrics and Digital Objects Task Force, OStrails, and FIDELIS, ensuring alignment between policy frameworks, technical specifications, and organisational sustainability. OStrails addresses interoperability gaps; FIDELIS strengthens the trust and capacity dimensions that enable sustained FAIR implementation. Together, they form complementary pillars of federation readiness.

Methodological Contributions and Limitations

Methodologically, the study contributes by (i) distinguishing repository-level infrastructure from data-level operational metadata; (ii) quantifying capability gaps across multiple FAIR dimensions rather than producing aggregate scores; and (iii) identifying conceptual confusion around metadata standards, informing future survey design and training activities.

4.1 Recommendations

Based on quantified gap magnitudes and support need convergence, we recommend five intervention priorities, three technical and two support-focused, for advancing EOSC Federation readiness:

Number of Priority	Priority Name	Types of Interventions	Description of Interventions
#1	DO-Level Granularity for PIDs and Rights Expression	Technical	Extend persistent identification and license metadata from the dataset level to the level of individual files and dataset components, enabling granular citation, machine navigation, partial reuse, and precise rights expression across heterogeneous and mixed-sensitivity datasets. Where minting separate object-level PIDs is not feasible, Signposting – which uses typed HTTP link headers to expose machine-readable pointers from landing pages to constituent objects – offers a practical, lower-cost path toward the same goal. For repositories managing collections with heterogeneous access conditions, extending machine-actionable rights expression to the object level is a necessary step toward automated reuse decisions in federated workflows.
#2	Provenance Interoperability Through Standard Vocabularies and Methods	Technical	Adopt standard vocabularies (e.g., PROV-O, RO-Crate) to replace proprietary lineage tracking, enabling automated reasoning about data origins, transformations, and dependencies across repositories.
#3	Policy Availability and Clarity in Metadata	Technical	Strengthen policy availability and structured exposure in metadata so that repository policies are easier to discover, interpret, and reuse across EOSC contexts.

#4	Shared Glossary for Operational Terminology and Use Cases	EOSC for Support	Establish a shared EOSC glossary with operational definitions of key FAIR and interoperability terms, explicitly linked to different use cases such as discovery, aggregation, provenance, rights expression, policy exposure, and reuse at deposit, file, and object level.
#5	Capacity Building and Sustained Support for FAIR Implementation	Support	Address the structural barriers that prevent repositories from translating FAIR endorsement into operational implementation. With 74% of repositories identifying funding and technical guidance as their primary support needs, and community coordination as a close third, targeted investment in training, shared tooling, and sustained community engagement is essential to enable progressive FAIR maturity – particularly for smaller and less-resourced repositories whose implementation gaps are most pronounced.

The European repository landscape stands at a pivotal transition: *from FAIR assessment to FAIR implementation*. Repositories show readiness, commitment, and shared support needs; what remains is coordinated action across the EOSC ecosystem—technical specification, policy guidance, funding allocation, and sustained community engagement—to translate willingness into operational, machine-actionable FAIR infrastructure.

Appendix 1: Interview Questions

1 Demographics

1.1 Interviewee

- Full Name
- Organization
- Role/position

If your job covers multiple roles, please select all that apply to you.

Repository manager

System developer/engineer Curator

Legal (advisor, officer, etc.) Policy advisor

Communications officer Collection manager

Board member

Other

- Email
- Are you involved in any EOSC-related projects or working groups? (Please specify)

1.2 Repository

- Name of repository
- What is the type of your repository?

Generalist

Thematic (e.g., imaging)

Mixed

Discipline specific (e.g. biodiversity)

DO-specific (e.g. workflows)

Other (please specify)

- Please provide the URL where this repository can be found and, if you have it, the DOI of its description in registries, like the e.g. RDA-endorsed [FAIRsharing](#)
- Country or region where the repository is based
- Type of organisation managing the repository

University / Research Performing Organisation
 Government body
 Private company
 Non-profit / NGO
 International organisation
 Other (please specify)

- Approximate number of datasets currently hosted

< 100
 100–999
 1000–10,000
 > 10,000
 Not sure

2 Technical

2.1 Metadata

- Do you have sources of metadata beyond DataCite?

Yes

- To what extent do you provide domain/community-specific

metadata? Repository generated

Depositor generated

Curator / Enriched

Other (please specify)

No

- Do you offer metadata in a standardised way? Recognized metadata

standards Generic Standards (e.g., JSON-LD or embedded metadata standards like Open Graph) Community-specific standards (of any kind, from any community), please specify No standards are followed.

- Are metadata sources discoverable from the PID/DOI landing page by navigation, or are there metadata sources (e.g., OGC-CSW, OAI-PMH, SPARQL) that cannot be accessed from the landing page?

All sources can be accessed directly from the landing page (e.g., via signposting or Linksets) through fully automated mechanisms

Some metadata can only be found via prior knowledge (some other mechanism for access, or by knowing the filename, for example); please specify

- Does your repository provide an unambiguous way to find Digital Object-specific or domain-specific metadata document(s) (e.g. from the depositor or curator, and related to the content of the data)

Yes

No

Maybe _____

- Do you support metadata assignment at the lowest level of granularity for a deposit (e.g., individual files within some container/dataset)? For example, metadata documents such as dictionaries, codebooks, variable catalogs, and schema files describe the data.

Yes

No

- Does your repository provide a clear, machine-actionable pointer for metadata individual records in a deposit?

Yes

No

Other _____

- Is the clear pointer resolvable to the data for records that can be openly

retrieved? Yes

No

- Do you share metadata with aggregator services (e.g., OpenAIRE, Google Dataset Search)?

Yes

No

If no, why not? _____

- Which interoperability protocols do you support?

OAI-PMH

REST API

SPARQL

OGC-CSW

Other (please specify) _____

None

- Do you use or map metadata to ontologies/controlled vocabularies (e.g., from [FAIRsharing](#), RDA, OBO, or other)?

Yes

No

Partially

If yes or partially, please specify _____

2.2 Licenses

2.2.1 DATA

- Is there a license on the DATA? (this is distinct from a reference to access

conditions) Yes

No

- Does the repository allow the depositor to select a license, or does the repository have a singular license for all DATA deposits?

Choice

Singular

No

- Is the license machine-discoverable? (There is a distinct metadata field in the record level metadata related to license)

Yes

No

- Does the data license use standards? For example, does it appear in the SPDX License List?

[Conditional to yes] Is the most common URL for the license used? (a universally accepted GUID) [Conditional to no] Is there another controlled license vocabulary used in-house? If yes, please specify

- If there is some other kind of “contract” related to the usage of the data, please specify_____
- Is the license machine-actionable?

Yes

Using what standards? _____

No

2.2.2 METADATA

- Do you require or allow a license for the metadata?

Yes

- Does the metadata license use a standard? For example, does it appear in the SPDX License List?
- Is the most common URL for the license used? (a universally

accepted GUID) No

- Is there another controlled license vocabulary used in-house?

Yes

If yes, please specify _____

No

- If not, is there some other kind of “contract” related to the usage

of the data? Yes

No

- Is the license machine-actionable?

Yes

Using what standards? _____

No

- Do you have different licenses for different kinds of metadata? (e.g. curated vs. deposited, fully-open vs authenticated access)

Yes

Please explain differences

No

2.3 Persistent Identifiers

- Does your repository assign PIDs to deposited items? Identifier

schemas Yes

No

- Which PID types do you support?

DOI

Handle

ARK

OID

URN

PURL

Other (please specify) _____

- Which resolver or PID infrastructure do you use?

handle.net

DataCite

local resolver

Other, please specify

- Do you assign PIDs to data within a deposit (e.g. files)?

Yes

- If yes, which? If non standard, please provide a link to the PID description site. _____

No

3 Operational

3.1 General Metadata Practices

- Does the metadata of your repository go through a validator?

Yes, metadata is validated automatically

Yes, metadata is validated manually

No, metadata is not validated

Unknown

- What does the validator target?

Data for compliance with community standards

Metadata compliance with community standards (e.g., minimum metadata checklists)

Metadata quality (checks if the fields introduced are correct, like validating ORCIDs, reference publications, etc)

Other _____

- List the most important standards that you validate. _____

3.2 Provenance

- Do you support provenance tracking for datasets (e.g., who created the data, how it was generated, version history)?

Yes, using standard vocabularies (e.g., PROV-O, RO-Crate)

Yes, internally (non-standard approach)

No

- How is this provenance information made available to users? (e.g., metadata, landing page, downloadable file) _____
- Do you provide users with contextual information that supports data

reusability? Data dictionaries or codebooks

Software or tools used to generate/analyze the data

Experimental methods or data collection protocols

Quality assurance or validation procedures

Version history, audit trail or changelog

Licensing and access conditions

Other (please specify)

(No)

- Is this information captured in a machine-readable way?

No

Yes

RO-Crate

JSON

RDF

Other (please specify)

- Do you link datasets to related outputs (e.g., publications, software,

workflows)? Yes

No

- Is it possible/required for data users to give back enriched versions of

a dataset? Yes, please explain how _____

No

3.3 FAIR Metrics

- Do you currently assess any FAIR metrics related to reusability (e.g., licensing clarity, metadata richness, provenance, interoperability)?

Yes

No

Partially

- If yes or partially, which ones and how are they implemented?
- Do you use any tools or services to measure FAIRness of datasets in your repository? Here a list of existing FAIR assessment/evaluation tools

F-UJI

FAIR Evaluator

FAIR-Aware

Other (please specify): _____

No

- Do you monitor or report the following aspects related to reusability?

Dataset citations

Downloads/views

Provenance completeness

Metadata completeness/accuracy

License clarity and standardization

Use of standard formats or vocabularies

Interlinking with related outputs (e.g., software, publications)

Other (please specify): _____

No

- What types of metrics would be useful but are currently not supported by your repository?

Metrics on dataset citations

Metrics on software or workflow reuse

Provenance completeness scores

Metadata richness/completeness scores

License clarity metrics

Compliance with domain-specific standards

Interlinking with other research outputs

Other (please specify)

There are no useful additional metrics

- What are the main barriers to tracking FAIR reusability metrics in your

repository? Lack of technical infrastructure

Lack of human resources or expertise

No clear community standards

Limited user demand or feedback

Lack of funding/support

Difficulty integrating external tools

Other (please specify)

None

4 Policy

4.1 General

- Does the repository follow any community guidelines for interoperability (e.g.

OpenAIRE Guidelines for interoperability)?

And if so, which one(s)?_____

- Does the repository have any of these types of policies: (Multiple)

Collection Policy

Preservation Policy / Data retention Policy

Open Access File Format Policy

Privacy Policy

Terms of Use Policy

Terms of Deposit

Ethical Use of Data Policy (e.g. CARE or Declaration of Helsinki)

FAIR Data Policy

User Registration and Authentication Policy

Data Curation Policy

Security Breach and Incident Response Policy

Data Quality Assessment Procedure

Other, please specify

No

- Are those policies machine-readable or exposed in metadata (e.g., schema.org, via registration in [FAIRsharing](#))?

Yes

No

Unknown

4.2 Rules and Regulations

- Are there legal regulations that affect the ability of your users to access data in your repository? for example, GDPR, Cloud Act, CIR High Value Datasets, Data Governance Act, EHDS, etc.

Yes, please specify_____

No

- Is there a time interval at which data records are reviewed or curated

(e.g. yearly)? Yes, please specify

No

5 Sustainability

- Does another organisation/ entity run the repository? Select the

applicable option: Yes

No

- If "Yes" is selected, What type of entity is this? Please select the type:

Private company

University / Research Performing Organisation

Government body

International body

Other (please specify)

- Which of the following measures are used by the repository? Please select all applicable measures:

Long-term funding

Community involvement

Collaborations

Data preservation strategies

Open access initiatives

Regular audits and evaluations

User training and support

Other (please specify)_____

6 EOSC Federation

- Do you agree with the principles of the EOSC Federation model? (e.g., distributed governance, federation of services, shared policies)

Strongly Agree

Somewhat Agree

Neither/Nor

Disagree

Strongly Disagree. Why: _____

- What's your view on the EOSC Federation approach – the idea of a coordinated network of independent but interoperable services? Do you see this working for your repository and community?" (Are there technical, policy-related, human resource related, or other challenges?) _____

- What kind of support would help you better align with EOSC initiatives

and policies? Technical guidance

Funding

Community building

Need no support

Cannot accept support

Other (please specify)_____

7 Any Further Remarks

Mark D Wilkinson, UPM Madrid, TF co-chair

Elli Papadopoulou, Athena RC, Greece, TF co-chair

Conflict of Interest Statements:

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